

Analysis of elastic wave modes sensing using piezoelectric and fiber Bragg grating sensors

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Abstract. This paper presents the results of the analysis of elastic guided wave sensing using three different size Piezoelectric Transducers (PZTs) and one Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor. Piezoelectric transducers are very popular in applications related to elastic wave generation and sensing in Structural Health Monitoring. The FBG sensors utilized in the past for quasi-static strain sensing are more and more utilized in the field of elastic wave sensing. The authors investigated the propagation of guided waves in a thin panel made out of isotropic material. Attention in this research was focused on the sensitivity analysis of different size PZTs and one FBG sensor from the point of view of symmetric and antisymmetric modes sensing.

Keywords: Guided waves, Piezoelectric transducer, FBG sensor, wave modes

1 Introduction

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is a reliable, efficient, and cost-effective method for increasing structural safety and lowering maintenance costs due to continuous structural state assessment of constructions. The application of SHM allows the avoidance of serious and critical structural failures due to early detection of defects. There are many defects that can generally occur in structures, like for example - cracks, corrosion, delamination, etc. There are several measurement approaches that are frequently employed for SHM based on vibration, electromechanical impedance, strain, or guided wave propagation measurements. To assess the health of a structure, the analysis of the collected data must be performed and should allow the undamaged (referential or pristine) structure to be distinguished from the damaged structure. SHM processes for structures are typically based on a comparison of known (healthy) and unknown (damaged) state data [1]. Among different types of SHM techniques guided Lamb wave propagation is getting more and more popular nowadays. These Lamb-wave-based techniques have demonstrated great potential for rapid damage detection in plate-like structures. Lamb wave generation and sensing are widely based on piezo-

electric transducers (PZT). Lamb waves are dispersive and have multimodal propagation. Due to this fact signal analysis is very complex. There are several reflections of multiple modes propagating in the structure and mode conversion. The solution is to use only the fundamental wave mode S_0 and A_0 and mode tuning techniques. Mode tuning allows one to choose such frequency for which the amplitude of one mode is significantly larger than the second mode. Such a frequency results from the properties and geometry of wave-generating or sensing elements.

Research related to the comparison of sensing properties of different sensors and their dimensions is very important because it allows for an increase in the sensitivity of the SHM system. Popular piezoelectric transducers due to connections via the metallic wires; are sensitive to EMI noises. There is a lack of such problems with FBG strain sensors based on fiber optics. This is very important in measurement in an explosive environment where the usage of electrical signals above certain power is forbidden. The FBG sensors were utilized for example for track assessment [2], rotorcraft structures [3], and acoustic emission sensing during the tensile test [4].

The research presented in this paper is related to the sensing sensitivity analysis in the case of Lamb wave propagation. PZT sensors with three diameters are utilized. Moreover, optical sensing based on FBG strain sensors is also investigated. Moreover, the S_0 and A_0 mode sensing comparison for PZT and FBG is investigated.

2 Setup

As shown in Fig. 1, the measurement setup includes a square aluminum plate with dimensions 1000 mm x 1000 mm x 1 mm, PZT sensors with different diameters, FBG sensor, and one piezoelectric transducer working as an actuator on the center of a plate. Fig. 1 also shows the measurement equipment and connections.

Fig. 1. Setup for elastic wave generation and sensing using PZT and FBG sensors.

The actuator located in the middle of the plate was generating a five-cycle sine signal modulated by a Hann window to excite elastic waves. Four sensors were utilized for the registration of the elastic wave propagation. The locations of the utilized FBG sensor (length 10 mm) and PZT sensors (diameters 10 mm, 20 mm, and 30 mm) are presented in Fig. 1. In the case of the PZT actuator and sensors the discs with a thickness of 0.5 mm made out of NCE51 material with wrap-around electrodes were utilized. The Femto Fibertech-manufactured FBGs were employed for optical-based elastic wave sensing. The laser source was an Apex AP1000 tunable laser. The signal from the generator is amplified by the Krohn Hite 7500 amplifier and drives the PZT actuator. The PXIe-5105 oscilloscope card was utilized for signal gathering from PZT and FBG sensors. Fig. 2 shows piezoceramic transducers in the form of discs with three diameters and wrap-around electrodes.

Fig. 2. Utilized piezoelectric transducers with wrap-around electrodes.

3 Methodology

Elastic wave generation was performed for the frequency range 50 kHz to 250 kHz (step 10 kHz). Elastic wave signals were registered by PZT and FBG sensors. Next, theoretical dispersion curves for aluminum plate were calculated. For this purpose numerical solution of Lamb equations (1) and (2) was performed.

$$\frac{\tan(qd)}{\tan(pd)} = \frac{-4k^2 pq}{(q^2 - k^2)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\tan(qd)}{\tan(pd)} = \frac{-(q^2 - k^2)^2}{4k^2 pq} \quad (2)$$

where:

$$p^2 = \left(\frac{\omega^2}{c_L^2} - k^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

$$q^2 = \left(\frac{\omega^2}{c_T^2} - k^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

and d – half of the plate thickness (in our case 0.5 mm), c_L – longitudinal wave velocity (6420 m/s), c_T – shear wave velocity (3040 m/s), ω – angular velocity [Hz], and k – wave number [1/m]. In Fig. 3 theoretical dispersion curves for a 1 mm-thick aluminum plate were presented. This result was achieved by the solution of equations (1) and (2). Based on the locations of the actuator and sensors, and theoretical dispersion curves time arrivals of elastic wave modes propagating in aluminum plate were calculated. In the investigated case in which waves in frequency in the range 50-250 kHz are excited, propagation only of fundamental S0 and A0 Lamb wave modes is observed. This region was marked in grey in the dispersion curves (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Dispersion curves for 1mm-thick aluminum plate.

Based on this fact the theoretical time of arrival (t_A) of S0 and A0 wave modes were calculated based on group velocities and propagation distance (actuator-sensor). The time duration of the excitation signal is calculated using the formula:

$$t_D = \frac{1}{f_m} = \frac{n_{cyc}}{f_c}, \quad (5)$$

where f_m – modulation frequency, f_c - carrier frequency, n_{cyc} – cycles number in time burst signal. Based on t_A and t_D , the propagating modes were identified in registered wave signals. For this purpose the time window is utilized to extract the portion of signals for the time range from t_A to $t_A + t_D$. This is performed for modes S0 and A0. Next using the developed MATLAB code maximum of wave packet in a portion of the signal extracted using the time window for S0 and A0 is picked. Based on the maximum wave packet in registered signals, its time of arrival (experimental) and maximum amplitude are determined.

Next experimental extracted S0 and A0 group velocities and amplitudes in the function of frequency were calculated. This procedure was performed for PZT sensors with diameters 10 mm, 20 mm, and 30 mm as well as FBG sensors. Next, the experimentally determined group velocities were compared with values from theoretical dispersion curves.

4 Results

In this section, the results of the analysis of experimental signals were presented. The aim was to identify the propagating S0 and A0 wave mode packets in the signals and determine their group velocities. Based on determined wave modes, its amplitude was extracted in the function of frequency. This is useful for frequency tuning of wave modes for selective mode generation and sensing.

4.1 Dispersion curves

Registered signals for FBG and PZT sensors were filtered using a bandpass filter related to the carrier excitation frequency before further processing. In Fig. 4 example of signals registered by FBG and PZT sensors for the frequency 60 kHz was presented. Signals also contain the envelopes created based on the Hilbert transform. In both signals, time windows based on arrival time t_A and duration time t_D of S0 and A0 modes from theoretical dispersion curves were located. In both windows maximum of the signal envelope is determined. Maxima was marked by circles. Based on this, the maximum amplitude and experimental time of arrival are extracted.

In the case of FBG signal (Fig. 4a), the first maxima is related to S0 wave mode and the second with A0 mode. In the case of the (10 mm diameter) PZT's signal (Fig. 4b) S0 mode packet was not determined correctly due to the crosstalk registered by the sensor (first wave packet). As was mentioned in the introduction piezoelectric transducers are prone to EMI. This is one of two problems related to the automatic maxima-picking algorithm for identification of wave packets.

Fig. 4. Mode identification on time signals for frequency 60 kHz, for:
a) FBG; b) PZT.

The second problem is illustrated in Fig. 5, which presents a signal gathered by FBG for a frequency of 140 kHz. In the case of A0 wave mode, two wave packets are located in the time window for A0 wave mode. This fact is related to modes overlapping due to multimodal propagation wave reflections and conversion at plate boundaries and PZT sensors.

Extracted automatically experimental time of arrivals of S0 and A0 modes were utilized for comparison with theoretical dispersion curves. Taking into account the potential problems with correct wave packet determination. It needs to be underlined that due to the picking of the time of maxima instead of the time of wave packet beginning, the half of excitation signal duration (t_D) need to be subtracted from the time instance of maxima. This procedure was conducted for one FBG and three PZTs with diameters respectively 10 mm, 20 mm, and 30 mm.

Fig. 5. Mode identification on time signal for FBG – frequency 140 kHz.

In Fig. 6 theoretical dispersion curves were compared with experimentally determined velocities of S0 and A0 wave mode for utilized four sensors. Propagation of S0 and A0 wave modes was identified. Some discrepancies in velocities are related to the two mentioned problems of mode identification in signals.

Fig. 6. Dispersion curves for a) FBG, b) PZT 10 mm, c) PZT 20 mm, d) PZT 30 mm.

4.2 Amplitudes of S0 and A0 wave modes

The next step was related to the analysis of amplitudes of S0 and A0 modes in the function of frequency. This was done by amplitudes for determined maxima for wave packets related to S0 and A0 wave modes in gathered signals. After collecting the amplitudes, the amplitudes were normalized in order to present the comparative amplitudes. This was done for both, S0 and A0 modes. Results in the form of S0 and A0 mode amplitudes in function of excitation frequency for FBG and PZT sensors were presented in Fig. 7.

In the case of the FBG sensor (Fig. 7a) amplitude of the S0 mode increases from 50 kHz to 210 kHz and then decreases. Maximum is located at frequency 210 kHz. The same trend is observed in the case of PZT with a diameter of 10 mm (Fig. 7b) where the maximum is for frequency 200 kHz. It needs to be underlined that FBG sensors have a length of 10 mm which is the same as the diameter of the smallest PZT. In the case of PZT with a diameter of 20 mm trend is similar but the maximum is located for frequency 160 kHz. In the case of PZT with a diameter of 30 mm, it was difficult to determine the S0 wave packet amplitudes for frequencies: 110 kHz – 150 kHz (Fig. 7c). This was due to complex signals caused by wave modes overlapping in time.

In the case of A0 wave mode for FBG (Fig. 7a) its amplitude decreases from a frequency of 50 kHz achieving a minimum of 160 kHz and then amplitude increases having a maximum of 210 kHz. In the case of PZT with a diameter of 10 mm, there is an agreement of results with FBG for a frequency range of 180-250 kHz. However, there is a problem for frequencies 50 and 60 kHz due to the mentioned signal crosstalk (see Fig. 4b). Moreover, it is hard to determine the amplitude trend for the frequency range 110-180 kHz – marked in grey in Fig. 7b). Wave packets were overlapping that does not allow to determine the correct time of arrivals and amplitudes of A0 mode. This could be noticed also as no agreement of the A0 mode experimental and theoretical velocities in Fig. 6b). In the case of PZT with a diameter of 20 mm, amplitudes of the A0 mode increase to maxima at 140 kHz and decrease rapidly. The problematic frequency region was also marked in gray. In the case of PZT with a diameter of 30 mm the A0 mode amplitude increases to 80 kHz, then there is valley for frequencies 110-140 kHz and maxima for 160 kHz. The region with the valley is problematic due to wave packet overlapping in the time. In the case of PZT with diameters 20 mm and 30 mm, there is no reference like it was in the case of 10 mm FBG and PZT with a diameter of 10 mm.

Fig. 7. Amplitudes of S0 and A0 modes in the function of excitation frequency for: a) FBG, b) PZT 10 mm, c) PZT 20 mm, d) PZT 30 mm.

The next step was related to the analysis of the elastic wave energy in the frequency domain. In this purpose time domain signals were transformed to the frequency domain using Fourier transformation. Next, for each excitation frequency, the maximum from the signal in the frequency domain was extracted. Results are presented in Fig. 8. In the case of FBG maximum is located for the frequency 200 kHz there is a valley for the frequency 130 kHz and a large amplitude for the frequency 50 kHz (Fig. 8a). In this analysis total wave energy (for both modes) is plotted so it is not possible to distinguish the A0 and S0 modes. In the case of PZT with a diameter of 10 mm, there is a maximum at frequency 210 kHz (Fig. 8b) which is similar to the A0 and S0 in time domain data (Fig. 7b). The overall trend of amplitude is similar to the case of S0 mode presented in Fig. 7b). In the case of PZT with diameter 20 mm, the maximum is achieved for frequency 160 kHz and trend is similar for S0 mode for time domain-based extracted amplitudes (Fig. 7c). Frequency domain based data could be utilized to verify the problematic results for region 110-180 kHz for time domain extracted amplitudes (Fig. 7c).

Fig. 8. Maximum of frequency spectrum for wave signals in the function of excitation frequency for a) FBG, b) PZT 10 mm, c) PZT 20 mm, d) PZT 30 mm.

In the case of PZT with a diameter of 30 mm (Fig. 8d), similar results for time domain-based extracted amplitudes of S0 and A0 mode (Fig. 7d) were achieved. There is also a valley for 110 -140 kHz for S0 and A0 mode amplitudes.

In Table 1 frequencies for maximum amplitude for S0 wave mode extracted based on time and frequency domain were compared with resonant frequencies of free and bonded to the plate PZT transducers. This comparison was conducted for the S0 wave mode because the achieved results are more reliable due to the lack of mode overlapping like for the A0 mode. It is because this is the fastest mode. Moreover, results in the form of S0 amplitudes in function of frequency were similar in the case of FBG with 10 mm length and PZT with 10mm diameter. The S0 mode amplitude maxima for time domain data were extracted from Fig. 7b-d) and for frequency domain from Fig. 8b-d). Frequencies of planar resonance of PZTs were determined by measuring its admittance spectra using a HIOKI IM3570 impedance analyzer and determination of admittance maxima. Measurements were performed for free PZT as well as PZTs bonded on the plate. There is an agreement of frequencies of maximum S0 amplitudes for PZT with a diameter of 10 mm and its resonant frequencies for free and bonded conditions (Table 1). In the case of PZT with diameters 20 and 30mm resonant frequencies are lower than frequencies for maximum S0 amplitudes for both free and bounded conditions. Bonding of the transducer caused the increase the stiffness what on turn increased the resonant frequencies of PZT. However, there are still some discrepancies in the results.

Table 1. Comparison of frequency for S0 amplitudes with resonant frequencies of free PZT.

	Frequency of S0 maximum amplitude [kHz] <i>time domain/frequency domain</i>	Frequency of PZT planar resonance (free) [kHz]	Frequency of PZT planar resonance (bonded) [kHz]
PZT 10 mm	210 / 210	206.0	212.8
PZT 20 mm	160 / 160	99.3	122.6
PZT 30 mm	100 / 90	68.2	87.3

This will be further studied by analysis of electromechanical impedance spectra of PZT and the influence of mode wavelength influence and its relation to sensor diameter on the mode sensitivity. The influence of mode wavelength on the sensor sensitivity will be investigated on theoretical data as well as experimentally based on full-wavefield scanning laser micrometry measurement. Full wavefield data will be also utilized for analysis of mode overlapping and possible improvement of mode identification.

5 Discussion

The presented results showed that it was possible to identify the S0 and A0 wave modes in signals registered by FBG and PZTs with different diameters. There were some discrepancies in the theoretical group velocities and experimentally extracted velocities. This is caused by mode overlapping in signals due to reflections from the boundary and sensors in the case of A0 mode. Small errors in the determination of time

of arrival cause large errors in the calculation of velocity. This could be also caused by a small distance between the actuator and the sensors.

In the case of amplitude in function of frequency for S0 mode similar results were achieved for FBG and PZT with 10 mm diameter. There are different regions of large sensitivity for S0 mode for PZT with different diameters. There were problems with the determination of A0 mode amplitudes in the function of frequency due. There was also crosstalk observed for PZTs because they are prone to EMI generated by the high voltage excitation signal.

Electromechanical impedance measurement allowed us to determine the resonant frequencies of PZT transducers. There was good agreement of resonant frequency of PZT with diameter 10 mm with maximum amplitude of S0 mode. There were larger differences in resonant frequency and maxima for S0 amplitudes for PZT with diameters 20 mm and 30 mm.

Further studies will be related to the analysis of electromechanical impedance spectra of PZT and the influence of mode wavelength influence to sensor diameter ratio on the mode sensitivity. Moreover, full wavefield data registered by scanning laser vibrometer will be utilized for auxiliary signal analysis and modes identification.

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